

Ground-UAV Platform Geometries for Radar Imaging

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Abstract — This paper provides a summary of comparative analysis pertaining to a systems trade study with platform geometries that encompass either one, two, or three distributed RF sensing platforms. The discussion is focused on analysis of a basic set of UAV trajectory parameters associated with performing sky-looking radar imaging. The baseline one-platform case corresponds to one ground-based radar transmitter/receiver. The two-platform case involves one ground-based radar transmitter/receiver and one UAV with a passive receiver and the three-platform case involves one ground-based radar transmitter and two UAV's each equipped with a passive receiver. This notional analysis is conducted with a narrow-bandwidth waveform within the L-Band region of the radar spectrum and notional parameters of the moon are adopted for the object-of-interest for radar imaging. Results indicate that the trajectories of the UAV's can be pre-selected to improve comparative radar imaging performance.

Index Terms — Radar Imaging, Agile UAV Sensor Trajectories, Space Imaging, GPS Receiver Technology

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper provides a summary of comparative analysis pertaining to a systems trade study with platform geometries that encompass either one, two, or three distributed RF sensing platforms. The discussion is focused on analysis of a basic set of UAV trajectory parameters associated with performing sky-looking radar imaging. The baseline one-platform case corresponds to one ground-based radar transmitter/receiver. The two-platform case involves one ground-based radar transmitter/receiver and one UAV with a passive receiver and the three-platform case involves one ground-based radar transmitter and two UAV's each equipped with a passive receiver.

As depicted in Fig. 1, notional parameters of the moon are adopted for modeling an object-of-interest and performing comparative multi-platform radar imaging trajectory analysis. Notional waveform parameters include 1 GHz center frequency and a narrow bandwidth of 5 MHz. This approach will enable the potential integration of the latest technology gains in narrowband L-Band GPS receiver front-ends into related analysis procedures for evaluating suitable radar imaging link budgets. For purposes of the analysis presented in this particular paper, image resolution using narrowband waveforms is adopted as the primary analysis and multi-platform trajectory evaluation metric.

Fig.1. Ground-UAV Radar Imaging Of Moon

For purposes of accessing basic multiplatform imaging resolution trends, the analysis in the following sections of this paper incorporate a number of approximations for earth-moon orbital geometries such as spherical bodies of motion with negligible wobble, estimation of mean radial distances between the earth and moon, as well as negligible relative rotational motions due to orbital synchronization. Orbital synchronization between the earth and the moon is illustrated in Fig. 2 and is denoted as “tidal lock” between earth and moon. This effect can, for example be observed on a daily basis where, for example, the earth rotates about 13- 14 degrees per day and the moon, likewise, revolves around the earth about 13-14 degrees on a given day.

Fig.2. Moon in Tidal Lock with Earth

For radar imaging applications, this tidal lock phenomenon has the effect of reducing the radar imaging configuration depicted in Fig. 1 from a general Multi-static ISAR (Inverse Synthetic Aperture Radar) geometry to the analysis of platform-by-platform bistatic radar imaging geometries. As illustrated in the basic trajectory and image resolution analysis in Section II, the resulting images considered from each bistatic Ground-UAV platform pair can be summed coherently to model the imaging capabilities of a given multi-platform configuration. Section III provides further analysis with regard to potential Ground-UAV trajectory patterns via the consideration of localized cloverleaf UAV patterns for bistatic radar imaging. This approach can be generalized to ISAR imaging for rotating objects-of-interest via the incorporation of relative rotational velocity estimation procedures.

II. UAV TRAJECTORIES AND IMAGING RESOLUTION

Fig. 3 shows a set of sample trajectory contours, denoted as C1 – C8, that are defined for illustrating a few radar imaging resolution calculations in this section. For purposes of illustration, resolution estimates are computed for the four point scatterers shown on the right half of Fig. 3. Fig 4 shows a sketch of Ground-UAV trajectory contour geometries for cloverleaf pattern analysis considered in the next section.

In Fig. 3, K_T represents the transmission path (or wavenumber vector) from the ground transmitter,

demarcated with an X symbol, to the moon. K_{R1} represents the scattering path to receiver R1 corresponding to one of the following trajectory contours: C1, C3, C5, or C7. K_{R2} represents the scattering path to receiver R2 corresponding to one of the following trajectory contours: C2, C4, C6, or C8.

Baseband signal models for the scattered signals at R1 and R2 (summed across the four point scatterers) can be modeled in the form of Eq. 1 [1]:

$$S_{R1,2} = \sum_{i=1}^4 \alpha_i \exp(-j2\pi f_l \tau_{ilm1,2}) \quad (1)$$

where the symbol $1,2$ denotes either R1 or R2, l is an index for discretized frequency values over the 5 MHz bandwidth, m represents pulse number, and $\tau_{ilm1,2}$ represents the total propagation delay to the i^{th} scatterer and back to R1 or R2 (for the m^{th} pulse and l^{th} frequency).

A relatively computationally intensive tomographic, or backprojection, image formation model corresponding to each trajectory contour for R1 or R2 can be modeled by the following pixel-by-pixel matched filter equation [1]:

$$I_{R1,2}(x, z) = \sum_{m=1}^{N_m} \sum_{l=1}^{N_l} S_{R1,2}(l, m) \cdot \exp(-j2\pi f_l \tau_{xzl m1,2}) \quad (2)$$

where $\tau_{xzl m1,2}$ denotes two-way propagation delay to associated with image plane pixel (x, z) . Images formed over two UAV receive contours, $I_{R1}(x, z)$ and $I_{R2}(x, z)$, can be coherently summed over the (x, z) image plane to

Fig.3. C1 – C8 Illustrate Basic Trajectory Contours for Sample Radar Resolution Estimates with Four Point Scatterers on Moon

generate the a multi-platform image [1].

Comparative radar imaging resolution analysis can be performed using combinations of the sample contours in Fig. 3 via estimates of trajectory-based deviations on spatial frequency wavenumber parameters such as K_x and K_z . For the Ground-UAV trajectory contours depicted in Fig. 3, maximum diffraction-limited image resolution limits can be computed as follows [2]:

$$\delta_x = \frac{2\pi}{\Delta K_x} \quad (3)$$

$$\delta_z = \frac{2\pi}{\Delta K_z} \quad (4)$$

Evaluation and analysis of Eq. 3 and Eq. 4 can be considered via numerical tabulation of resolution values associated with the combination of the following two sets of contours shown in Fig. 3.

E1: Combinations of Localized Trajectory Contours C1, C2, C5, C6

- C1 Combined With C2 Over .5 Degree Latitude Interval

$$K_{z1} \approx \frac{4\pi f}{c} \cos\left(\frac{.25^\circ}{2}\right) \sin(.125^\circ) = .1828 m^{-1} \quad (5)$$

$$K_{z2} \approx \frac{4\pi f}{c} \cos\left(\frac{.25^\circ}{2}\right) \sin(-.125^\circ) = -.1828 m^{-1} \quad (6)$$

$$\delta_z = \frac{2\pi}{K_{z1}-K_{z2}} \approx 17 m \quad (7)$$

$$K_{x1} \approx \frac{4\pi f}{c} \cos\left(\frac{0^\circ}{2}\right) \sin(0^\circ) = 0 m^{-1} \quad (8)$$

$$K_{x2} \approx \frac{4\pi f}{c} \cos\left(\frac{0^\circ}{2}\right) \sin(-0^\circ) = 0 m^{-1} \quad (9)$$

$$\delta_x = \frac{2\pi}{K_{x1}-K_{x2}} \approx \infty m \quad (10)$$

- C5 Combined With C6 Over .5 Degree Longitude Interval

$$K_{z1} \approx \frac{4\pi f}{c} \cos\left(\frac{0^\circ}{2}\right) \sin(0^\circ) = 0 m^{-1} \quad (11)$$

$$K_{z2} \approx \frac{4\pi f}{c} \cos\left(\frac{0^\circ}{2}\right) \sin(0^\circ) = 0 m^{-1} \quad (12)$$

$$\delta_z = \frac{2\pi}{K_{z1}-K_{z2}} \approx \infty m \quad (13)$$

$$K_{x1} \approx \frac{4\pi f}{c} \cos\left(\frac{.25^\circ}{2}\right) \sin(.125^\circ) = .1828 m^{-1} \quad (14)$$

Fig.4. Localized Cloverleaf Trajectory Contours for Sample Radar Resolution Estimates with Four Point Scatterers on Moon

$$K_{X2} \approx \frac{4\pi f}{c} \cos\left(\frac{.25^\circ}{2}\right) \sin(-.125^\circ) = -3.72 \text{ m}^{-1} \quad (27)$$

$$= -1.1828 \text{ m}^{-1} \quad (15)$$

$$\delta_X = \frac{2\pi}{K_{X1}-K_{X2}} \approx 17 \text{ m} \quad (16)$$

$$\delta_X = \frac{2\pi}{K_{X1}-K_{X2}} \approx 1 \text{ m} \quad (28)$$

E2: Combinations of Offset Trajectory Contours C3, C4, C7, C8

- C3 Combined With C4 Over Two Discontiguous .25 Degree Latitude Sub-Intervals Spaced 20 Degrees Apart And Symmetric About The Ground Transmitter

$$K_{Z1} \approx \frac{4\pi f}{c} \cos\left(\frac{10.25^\circ}{2}\right) \sin(5.125^\circ) = 3.72 \text{ m}^{-1} \quad (17)$$

$$K_{Z2} \approx \frac{4\pi f}{c} \cos\left(\frac{10.25^\circ}{2}\right) \sin(-5.125^\circ) = -3.72 \text{ m}^{-1} \quad (18)$$

$$\delta_Z = \frac{2\pi}{K_{Z1}-K_{Z2}} \approx 1 \text{ m} \quad (19)$$

$$K_{X1} \approx \frac{4\pi f}{c} \cos\left(\frac{0^\circ}{2}\right) \sin(0^\circ) = 0 \text{ m}^{-1} \quad (20)$$

$$K_{X2} \approx \frac{4\pi f}{c} \cos\left(\frac{0^\circ}{2}\right) \sin(-0^\circ) = 0 \text{ m}^{-1} \quad (21)$$

$$\delta_X = \frac{2\pi}{K_{X1}-K_{X2}} \approx \infty \text{ m} \quad (22)$$

- C7 Combined With C8 Over Two Discontiguous .25 Degree Longitude Sub-Intervals Spaced 20 Degrees Apart And Symmetric About The Ground Transmitter

$$K_{Z1} \approx \frac{4\pi f}{c} \cos\left(\frac{0^\circ}{2}\right) \sin(0^\circ) = 0 \text{ m}^{-1} \quad (23)$$

$$K_{Z2} \approx \frac{4\pi f}{c} \cos\left(\frac{0^\circ}{2}\right) \sin(0^\circ) = 0 \text{ m}^{-1} \quad (24)$$

$$\delta_Z = \frac{2\pi}{K_{Z1}-K_{Z2}} \approx \infty \text{ m} \quad (25)$$

$$K_{X1} \approx \frac{4\pi f}{c} \cos\left(\frac{10.25^\circ}{2}\right) \sin(5.125^\circ) = 3.72 \text{ m}^{-1} \quad (26)$$

$$K_{X2} \approx \frac{4\pi f}{c} \cos\left(\frac{10.25^\circ}{2}\right) \sin(-5.125^\circ)$$

In summary, since the point scatterers depicted in the geometry of Fig. 3 are all at equal range to the ground transmitter, a narrowband (i.e. $f = 1$ GHz with 5 MHz bandwidth) monostatic radar analysis on a ground-based radar imaging geometry indicates that none of the four scatterers can be resolved for this particular case. The sample calculations above indicate that various multi-platform Ground-UAV geometries can be defined that can provide significant levels of radar imaging resolution. Completely symmetric geometries with discontiguous trajectory contours as illustrated in example E2 can provide high-resolution radar imaging capabilities; but, on the other hand, can often be associated with imaging artifacts such as grating lobes in the system impulse response. These type of artifacts can often be mitigated by adding a degree of randomized dis-symmetries to these type of discontiguous (and sparse) contours.

III. PROGRAMMABLE UAV CLOVERLEAF PATTERNS

This section provides an analysis of cloverleaf-type UAV trajectories as depicted in Fig. 4. A number of mathematical formulations exist for potential application towards designing and programming Ground-UAV contour trajectories for radar imaging. For, example, Fig. 5 illustrates a set of planar cloverleaf-type curves developed for investigating “humanoid” robotic arm movements [3]. Parametric equations for these planar polar contours can be formulated for purposes of covering a desired portion of the $K_X - K_Y$ space with conveniently realizable contour trajectories.

Fig.5. Generalized Cloverleaf Patterns [3]

For example, one set of parametric equations that describe the generalized cloverleaf patterns in Fig. 5 are as follows [3]:

$$x = \cos(3\theta(t)) - \epsilon \cdot \cos(\theta(t)) \quad (29)$$

$$z = \sin(3\theta(t)) - \epsilon \cdot \sin(\theta(t)) \quad (30)$$

where $\epsilon = .3$ for a four-branch cloverleaf that is somewhat similar to the pattern depicted in Fig. 4.

Many other interesting examples of generalized cloverleaf patterns known as “rose patterns” can be described by the following sinusoidal polar forms [4] [5] similar to Eq. 31:

$$r = a + b \cdot \cos(k\theta) \quad (31)$$

Fig. 6 illustrates two parametric sample curves of Eq. 31. The plot on the left corresponds to $a=1$, $b=1$, and $k=3/2$. The plot on the right corresponds to $a=1$, $b=3$, and $k=1$. Some potential features of some of these types of trajectory contours include overlapping intervals (i.e. overlapping circles) where radar imaging can be performed on each interval separately and then registered for coherence. Also, trajectory contours that are concentric can enable fast lower-resolution image formation over smaller inner trajectory intervals and then higher-resolution images formation over adaptively selectable larger outer contours.

Alternatively, one potential approach to joint trajectory design and radar imaging is to investigate trajectory contours that are parallel with the imaging coordinates over relatively large intervals. For example, the particular cloverleaf sketched in Fig. 4 overlaps the center latitude and longitude lines over very large portions of the inner trajectory. This characteristic can enable two separate image formation steps where one image is formed in the z-dimension and another image is formed in the x-dimension. Afterwards, the images can be combined to form a narrowband radar image in the x-z cross-range plane. As illustrated in Fig. 8, one half of this type of trajectory contour can be described by the following set of rotated figure-8 equations:

Fig.6. Two Sample Rose Patterns

$$r = [2.5 \cdot 10^9 \cdot \cos(2\theta) \cdot \sec^4(\theta)]^{1/2} \quad (32)$$

$$x = r \cdot \cos\left(\theta + \frac{\pi}{4}\right) \quad (33)$$

$$z = r \cdot \sin\left(\theta + \frac{\pi}{4}\right) \quad (34)$$

This approach to relatively computationally efficient radar imaging [6] can be illustrated by considering the Fourier spectrum for the 4-scatterer geometry depicted in Fig. 3 and Fig 4:

$$\overrightarrow{KCX}(l, m) = \sum_i^4 \frac{4\pi f_l x_{im}}{c} \cos\left(\frac{B_m}{2}\right) \vec{u} \quad (35)$$

$$\overrightarrow{KCZ}(l, m) = \sum_i^4 \frac{4\pi f_l z_{im}}{c} \cos\left(\frac{B_m}{2}\right) \vec{u} \quad (36)$$

where B_m is the bistatic bisector angle between the transmitter and receiver for pulse m and \vec{u} is the pulse-by-pulse unit vector from the bistatic bisector to scene center. x_{im} , z_{im} represents the differential range from the bistatic bisector point (or range) to scene center and the range to the bistatic bi-sector point for the i^{th} scatterer on a per pulse basis.

Fig. 9 is a depiction of a radar image for the CX trajectory contour evaluated over a .5 degree integration angle-cut through the transmitter (denoted by the X in Fig. 8) and Fig. 10 is a depiction of a radar image for the CZ trajectory contour evaluated over a .5 degree integration angle-cut through the transmitter. These two images correspond to the CX and CZ trajectory sub-interval contours and are formed via direct inverse FFT of the respective Fourier spectrum. Spectral interpolation, or polar re-formatting, is not required in this case since the length of the CX and CZ sub-interval contours are considerably less than the radial distance from the earth to scene center and, therefore, \overrightarrow{KCX} , \overrightarrow{KCZ} , and B_m are in approximate rectangular coordinates via small-angle approximations. For this particular example, the two resulting images are combined via a scaling, rotation, translation, and non-coherent summation process as follows:

$$\mathbf{KCX} = \frac{4\pi}{c} \sum_i^4 \vec{f}_l \left[\overline{x_{im} \cos\left(\frac{B_m}{2}\right)} \right]^T \quad (37)$$

$$\mathbf{KCZ} = \frac{4\pi}{c} \sum_i^4 \vec{f}_l \left[\overline{z_{im} \cos\left(\frac{B_m}{2}\right)} \right]^T \quad (38)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{I}(x, z) &= \left| \text{IFFT}\left(\exp(j \cdot \mathbf{KCX} \cdot \mathbf{R}_{\vec{u}})\right) \right| \\ &\quad + \mathbf{T} \cdot \left| \text{IFFT}\left(\exp(j \cdot \mathbf{KCZ} \cdot \mathbf{R}_{\vec{u}})\right) \right| \\ &= |\mathbf{I}(x, y)| + \mathbf{T} \cdot |\mathbf{I}(z, y)| \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

where Eq. 37 – Eq. 40 represent matrix operations for efficient coding in a Matlab environment and \mathbf{T} represents

Fig.8. Sample of Rotated Figure Eight Pattern (or Half-Cloverleaf) That Aligns Well With X-Z Axis

Fig.9. Sample Image for Geometry in Fig. 4 Computed Over a Portion of Trajectory Sub-Interval CX in Fig. 8

Fig.10. Sample Image for Geometry in Fig. 4 Computed Over a Portion of Trajectory Sub-Interval CZ in Fig. 9

Fig.11. Sample Image Generated Via Non-Coherent Combination of CX and CZ Images In Fig. 9 and Fig. 10

a matrix operator for scaling, rotation, and translation. The resulting radar image, $I(x, z)$, is shown in Fig. 11. The sidelobe levels are relatively high since, for this particular example, a convolutional window function is not multiplied by the two exponential impulse response functions in Eq. 40.

In summary, a number of issues pertaining to the analysis of multi-platform Ground-UAV geometries are discussed in this paper. The focus of the discussion is narrowband radar imaging in situations where a single monostatic ground platform does not provide significant levels of resolution. The specific techniques that are formulated and discussed are realistic and efficient from two joint perspectives: 1) analysis of programmable trajectory contours that enable straightforward radar image formation processing and 2) analysis of programmable trajectory contours that are flexible and efficient from a robotic controls viewpoint. In addition, while the focus of this paper is on radar imaging analysis, the basic analytical treatment is compatible with recent trends in state-of-the-art narrowband L-Band receiver technologies for purposes of meeting receiver sensitivity and link budget requirements.

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